

Basal Ganglia Neurons in Healthy and Parkinsonian Primates Generate Recurring Sequences of Spikes

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- Supplementary material -

Supplementary table

			Pooled data (monkeys 1 and 2)				Monkey 1				Monkey 2			
			Median (IQR)	n	p (comp. to shuffled)	p (MPTP vs normal)	Median (IQR)	n	p (comp. to shuffled)	p (MPTP vs normal)	Median (IQR)	n	p (comp. to shuffled)	p (MPTP vs normal)
GPe	Prop. spikes in sequ.	Normal	0.4176 (0.1036)	38	0.000	0.000	0.4116 (0.1500)	13	0.000	0.005 (38)	0.4192 (0.0896)	25	0.000	0.000
		MPTP	0.3032 (0.9280)	40	0.000		0.3132 (0.1168)	15	0.001		0.2980 (0.0872)	25	0.004	
	Prop. time in sequ.	Normal	0.3289 (0.1242)	38	0.001	0.000	0.3228 (0.1261)	13	0.000	0.003 (34)	0.3451 (0.0980)	25	0.148	0.000
		MPTP	0.2196 (0.0921)	40	0.868		0.2286 (0.0860)	15	0.804		0.2196 (0.1268)	25	1.000	
STN	Prop. spikes in sequ.	Normal	0.2016 (0.0296)	13	0.001	0.001	0.1992 (0.0332)	12	0.002	0.000 (18)	0.2064	1	-	0.643
		MPTP	0.2604 (0.0840)	27	0.000		0.2732 (0.0852)	14	0.001		0.251 (0.0768)	13	0.002	
	Prop. time in sequ.	Normal	0.1595 (0.3518)	13	0.006	0.151	0.1595 (0.0579)	12	0.012	0.322 (64)	0.1570	1	-	0.571
		MPTP	0.1885 (0.0696)	27	0.002		0.1885 (0.0551)	14	0.025		0.1852 (0.0668)	13	0.027	
GPi	Prop. spikes in sequ.	Normal	0.3608 (0.1132)	33	0.024	0.594	0.2932 (0.0736)	17	0.194	0.527 (118)	0.3960 (0.0816)	16	0.064	0.093
		MPTP	0.3460 (0.0720)	34	0.000		0.3204 (0.0756)	16	0.001		0.3600 (0.1028)	18	0.000	
	Prop. time in sequ.	Normal	0.3083 (0.1176)	33	0.548	0.291	0.2497 (0.0671)	17	0.145	0.631 (122)	0.3565 (0.0851)	16	0.632	0.064
		MPTP	0.2772 (0.0721)	34	0.000		0.2514 (0.0670)	16	0.011		0.3116 (0.0667)	18	0.004	

Shown are median and inter-quartile range (IQR) of the proportion of spikes in sequences (prop. spikes in sequ.) and the proportion of time in sequences (prop. time in sequ.) in the normal and parkinsonian states, in pooled data from both animals, and separated by animal. Comparisons to shuffled inter-spike interval (ISI) representations were done using the paired Wilcoxon test, while comparison between data from the normal and parkinsonian states were carried out with Mann-Whitney tests. Abbreviations: GPe, external pallidal segment; GPi, internal pallidal segment; STN, subthalamic nucleus; MPTP, 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (refers to animals treated with MPTP).

A. Proportion of ISIs in sequences

B. Proportion of time in sequences

C. Duration of Sequences

Supplementary figure 1: Proportion of ISIs in sequences (A), proportion of time spent in sequences (B), and duration of 2-|SI sequences (C). The layout of this figure is identical to that in figure 3 of the main text. However, the data shown in this figure were generated with a proportional cut-off value of 0.005. See main text for additional details.

A. Proportion of ISIs in sequences

B. Proportion of time in sequences

C. Duration of Sequences

Supplementary figure 2: Proportion of ISIs in sequences (A), proportion of time spent in sequences (B), and duration of 2-ISI sequences (C). The layout of this figure is identical to that in figure 3 of the main text. However, the data shown in this figure were generated with a proportional cut-off value of 0.05. See main text for additional details.

A. Proportion of ISIs in sequences

B. Proportion of time in sequences

C. Duration of Sequences

Supplementary figure 3: Proportion of ISIs in sequences (A), proportion of time spent in sequences (B), and duration of 2-ISI sequences (C). The layout of this figure is identical to that in figure 3 of the main text. However, the data shown in this figure were generated with a time cut-off value of 1 ms. See main text for additional details.

A. Proportion of ISIs in sequences

B. Proportion of time in sequences

C. Duration of Sequences

Supplementary figure 4: Proportion of ISIs in sequences (A), proportion of time spent in sequences (B), and duration of 2-ISI sequences (C). The layout of this figure is identical to that in figure 3 of the main text. However, the data shown in this figure were generated with a time cut-off value of 2 ms. See text for additional details.

A. Proportion of ISIs in sequences

B. Proportion of time in sequences

C. Duration of Sequences

Supplementary figure 5: Proportion of ISIs in sequences (A), proportion of time spent in sequences (B), and duration of 2-ISI sequences (C). The layout of this figure is identical to that in figure 3 of the main text. However, the data shown in this figure were generated with a time cut-off value of 4 ms. See text for additional details.